

Speculation on Scaling, Maximum Entropy and Free Particle Quantum Mechanics Part 4

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In Parts I to 3, we argued that rest mass, m_0 , in a rest frame or energy E in a moving frame represents a probability for an internal event to happen in time. This suggests a period for internal events to occur on average of $\text{constant}/m_0$ or $\text{constant}/E$. In space, $|p|$ (momentum) is the probability for internal spatial events and the repeated length is \hbar/p . In other words, one has a uniform probability within \hbar/E regions in time and $\hbar/|p|$ regions in space on average.

This, however, begs the question: What does one do for p and $-p$ (in one dimension)? P momentum= $\hbar/\text{wavelength}$ represents a constant (uniform probability), but if one has p_1 and $-dp_1$, then an AND situation should yield a p_1-dp_1 uniform probability. There needs to be a mathematical way in which to express the product of this AND situation. In addition, one needs to deal with OR situations. If p means length regions of \hbar/p , these must be denoted somehow, namely by 0 probability points to show that a cycle is starting or has finished. This means that p_1 and p_2 have different 0 points along the x axis. In an OR situation, one might have one or the other and so one must find a way to obtain a scheme.

As a result, one must go beyond the $P_{\text{internal}} = p dx$ uniform probability equation and find a new probability which incorporates this uniformity, but accounts for AND and OR situations with other p or dx values. As a result, one has a $P_1(P \text{ cumulative})$ where $P_1 = \exp(i \text{ argument})$ probability with an internal cumulative probability: $\int (\text{endpoint}, x) p dx$ representing a uniform distribution.

Uniform Probability

The main idea presented in Parts I to III is that m_0 (in the case of a rest particle) or E for a moving one represent a probability for an internal event (e.g. a decay) in time. This suggests that $\text{constant}/E$ and $\text{constant}/m_0$ represent average time lengths between such probabilistic events, i.e. define a kind of internal resolution in time. In space, it was argued that $|p|$ (momentum) represents probability for some kind of internal event. Thus, one would have the uniform distribution in space:

Probability(x) = dx/L so $p dx$ means that $p = \hbar/L$ unit where $L = \text{wavelength}$ and \hbar is a constant. ((1))

AND Situations with Different Momentum Values

The above ideas beg the question: What does one do with a negative p ? If one has p_1 and $-dp_1$, then the overall momentum is p_1-dp_1 and this represents a different uniform probability. One should be able to express this as an AND situation such that:

$$P_1(p) P_1(-dp) = P_1(p - dp) \quad ((2))$$

The uniform probability representation ((1)) does not allow this in a simple manner, even though the idea of uniformity within a wavelength region is key. Nevertheless, one needs another probability expression which incorporates the uniformity represented by p_x , but satisfies ((2)). This suggests a power law probability for P_1 which means one may use \exp as the base constant. Instead of having only $P_1(p)$, one should have $P_1(p_x)$ because p_x represents the uniform distribution. Furthermore, one has periodicity and so one should use:

$$\exp(ip_x) \quad ((3))$$

We have obtained ((3)) in previous notes, but here we try to do so by starting with a uniform distribution in space, $p_x = \int p \, dx$, and incorporating it in a second probability function which allows for AND situations.

Creating a periodic function in x , however, means that one must reduce probability at the endpoints of \hbar/p compared to the interior, but at the same time must respect the uniform distribution p_x . In other words, this new probability is no longer the uniform distribution, but is based on it. As a result, the uniform distribution p_x (which is a kind of cumulative probability because $p_x = \int p \, dx$) is the argument of a shell periodic function which creates a new probability function which respects AND conditions. This shell function $\exp(ip_x)$ not only creates periodicity, but involves negative and positive probabilities in $\cos(p_x)$ and $\sin(p_x)$. We already saw, however, that for the uniform distribution p_1 and $-p_1$ represent positive and negative probabilities because overall momentum represents probability in the uniform case.

Thus, we suggest that:

$$\exp(ip_x) = P_1(P_{\text{cumulative}}(x)) \quad \text{where } P_{\text{cumulative}}(x) = \int (\text{endpoint to } x) p \, dx \quad ((4))$$

The cumulative probability $P_{\text{cumulative}}$ means that $d/dx P_{\text{cumulative}} = p$. ((5))

This shows how the d/dx translational operator appears in this scheme. This same operator appears in Fisher's information. Here it pulls out one probability embedded in another.

The OR Situation

We now try to examine the OR result based on $\exp(ip_x)$. For p_1 and p_2 , as noted above, the uniform probability regions are \hbar/p_1 and \hbar/p_2 . Given the shell probability, $\exp(ip_x)$, simply adding $\exp(ip_1x) + \exp(ip_2x)$ means that neither 0 points linked to p_1 or p_2 are zero points of the OR probability unless $p_1 = -p_2$. (Here 0 points refer to real or imaginary zero points of the function.)

Given the average viewpoint of p representing spatial events, one would expect that p_1 and p_2 in an OR situation should give rise to a different overall p scheme. If one writes:

$$\exp(ip_1x)(1 + \exp(-ip_1x + ip_2x)) \quad ((6)) \quad \text{then}$$

$$\text{Real part: } \cos(p_1x)\{1 + \cos((-p_1 + p_2)x)\} - \sin(p_1x)\sin((-p_1 + p_2)x) \quad ((7a))$$

Imaginary part: $\sin(p_1x) \{1 + \cos(-p_1+p_2)x\} + \cos(p_1x)\sin(-p_1+p_2)x$ ((7b))

For the case of $p_2=-p_1$, one has the simple result of $2\cos(p_1x)$.

Thus, an OR situation for two uniform probabilities using a shell $\exp(ipx)$ approach, leads to a nontrivial result ((7a)).

Why is the Cumulative Shell $\exp(ipx)$ Needed?

In Part II, we argued that one may use the idea of a uniform distribution p_x within a wavelength \hbar/p region to solve one dimensional reflection-refraction. One does not actually need to use the shell probability $\exp(ipx)$. In such a case, however, the n_1-n_2 junction point, x_0 , can be made to lie within a wavelength of the incident, reflected and refracted photons/particles.

In a usual problem, one deals with all x points. When taking averages, AND situations lead to new p values being created and these must emerge from the probability mathematics. Thus, as argued above, the uniform distribution p_x is not sufficient.

As a result, what is considered to be smooth motion in x for a constant velocity is not. The breaking of space into \hbar/p units for a constant p requires a sensing of space units by a particle through $\exp(ipx)$, but within this one has the uniform distribution p_x .

Conclusion

In conclusion, in Parts I-III, we argue for the existence of a uniform distribution in time with probability m_0 (for a particle at rest) and E for a moving one. This leads to time units of length constant \hbar/m_0 or \hbar/E which correspond to average internal events like decay. For space, we suggest a probability of p and length units of \hbar/p .

Here, we argue that one must also consider AND and OR scenarios involving different p values as well as the $-p$ case. If one has p and $-dp$, this means a reduction in the probability used in the uniform distribution. One has to be able to mathematically multiply two probability functions to obtain the AND result, but one cannot multiply p and $-dp$. This suggests a new probability function with p_x , the uniform distribution, as its argument. This is like a convolution of two probability functions. As a result, we argue for $\exp(ipx)$ which contains the shell probability $\exp(i \text{ argument})$ with argument = Integral (endpoint, x) $p dx$, i.e. a cumulative uniform probability.

As a result, we argue that motion in space with constant velocity and p is not fully smooth, but is based on the uniform distribution p_x restricted to \hbar/p length units.